

Investigation in Gassy Ozone Influence on Flaxes Made from Biologically Activated Whole Wheat Grains Quality Parameters

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Abstract : The aim of the current research was to investigate the gassy ozone effect on quality parameters of flaxes made from whole biologically activated wheat grains. The research was accomplished on in year 2012 harvested wheat grains variety 'Zentos'. Grains were washed, wetted; grain biological activation was performed in the climatic chamber up to 24 hours. After biological activation grains was compressed; than flaxes was dried in convective drier till constant moisture content $9\pm 1\%$. For grain treatment gassy ozone concentration as 0.0002% and treatment time - 6 min was used. In the processed flaxes the content of A and G tocopherol decrease by 23% and by 9%; content of B2 and B6 vitamins - by 11% and by 10%; elaidic acid - by 46%, oleic acid - by 29%; arginine (by 80%), glutamine (by 74%), asparagine and serine (by 68%), valine (by 62%), cysteine (by 54%) and tyrosine (by 47%).

Keywords : gassy ozone, flaxes, biologically activated grains, quality parameters, treatment

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